

Open Schooling in the Sustainable Development Reserve of Tupé Amazon rainforest.

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Abstract: The objective of this study is to promote reflexive discussions among students, researchers, and local communities to collectively protect life in Amazon rainforest. The study presents open schooling activities that learners and community members of Tupé a sustainable Development Reserve located in Amazon developed with researchers from UFAM University and the CONNECT Project. One of the results of this studies is a map about questions that we discussed which will enable to continue the discussion and develop new studies.

1. INTRODUCTION:

This study is based on the open schooling activities in one of the six communities of the Tupé sustainable development reserve, on the banks of the Negro River, located in the countryside 25 km as the crow flies from the city of Manaus in the state of Amazonas, Brazil.

The Tupé region, a rural area in the municipality of Manaus, is one of the territories affected by climate change, both in terms of worsening droughts and floods, exacerbating socio-economic and environmental challenges.

According to studies by Borges, Silva and Muller (2021), the community experiences many difficulties in relation to public policies, since there is a lack of public sanitation, health centres and public transportation.

The citizens have a low income and survive on small-scale farming, fishing, tourism, and commerce. The Sustainable Development Reserve's education system is supported by three types of learning: informal, which refers to the appreciation of local and community knowledge, present in the Amazonian way of life; non-formal, which relates to community projects, organized by external or internal agents and which has an organized cycle and objectives; and formal education linked to the systematized knowledge of the school and its regular training. This triad of the training process enables different critical contexts in which communities come to recognize their place in protecting the culture and heritage of traditional communities.

This report investigates the factors affecting the livelihoods of the São João do Tupé community. By highlighting the opinions of young people and adults in the community, through open schooling for responsible citizenship our research presents a vivid collective picture of the climate disruptions affecting the community.

In order to intervene, it is necessary to invest in education and reflect, research, and innovate collectively using the basis of responsible research and innovation.

2. PROCEDURES

Open schooling was introduced as a set of learning activities to discuss problems that are important for our community and includes students from different ages – children and teenagers, teachers, as well people of our community and from the universities who work with research.

The activities that we developed were based on the model CARE-KNOW-DO which is a way to make learning more useful and connected to the things that we care about, and we want to know more about and also do something about.

The discussion encourages all members to be involved in problem-solving and research about the subject. So what we learn matches with what students we are interested in and need to know to take actions. In our understanding

- CARE: This is about learning informally from professionals and family members. It helps students connect with real-life problems and issues that matter to them.
- KNOW: This is about learn new things and involves also learn how to research to find answers with sources and people. It's like studying and discussing facts and information to increase our understanding with different opinions.
- DO: This is about taking action, making decisions or do something practical based on what we have learned.

3. ABOUT TUPÉ COMMUNITY

The Tupé Sustainable Development Reserve in the Amazon is like a special place where we protect nature and make life better for the people who live there.

1. People who have lived here for a long time use the land and trees to survive, and we also taking care of the environment.
2. Visitors can only get to this place by traveling on the Negro River. It takes about 30 minutes to 1.5 hours to get there from a city called Manaus.
3. It's easier to move around in boats when it's rainy (January to May), but it's harder during the dry season (June to October).
4. We really care about the people who live there, their culture, and the forests and rivers.
5. In the Amazon, there are lots of different groups of indigenous people with their own languages, cultures, and traditions. Some you might have heard of, like the Yanomami, Kayapó, Tikuna, and Munduruku. But there are also smaller groups, like the Tuyuka and Dessana, who are part of Tupé.
6. The local people also use their culture to welcome tourists. They dance, sing, and make things like musical instruments, bracelets, necklaces, and headdresses to share with visitors. This helps people make money to support their families.

So, in simple words, Tupé is a special place where people live in harmony with nature, protect their culture, and welcome tourists to learn and appreciate nature with us.

4. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Participants worked in small groups and also shared their views with everyone too, with discussions and drawings. The conversation was mapped including the questions.

Figure 1 - Drawing using paper

Figure 2 - Drawing using tablet

These are some of the views that participants shared in groups, drawing and writing.

"I wish that we had a house and boat." boy

I love the landscape where I live, and I want to see improvements for my riverside community". girl

"What I ask for the community is that we be strong, in the sense of union, of wanting, of having the will to join and do things. Because when we really want it, we do it". A community member grandmother

Thinking about the Amazon means considering its diverse social and cultural contexts, in which the sustainability debate should generate valuable insights for local communities regarding the integration of economic, social, cultural, and environmental dimensions." - Amazonian academic researcher.

What participants learned:

- 1. We learned what open schooling means and how it works.*
- 2. We found out about new ways to work together to discuss problems, like using research maps, drawing, thinking and talking.*
- 3. We got better at understanding problems and figuring out how to search for possibilities with these new ideas.*

These are the questions that participants mapped supported by researchers.

Figure 3 –Inquiry Mapping of the Community supported by the researchers

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